

Molecular Complexes of Tetracycline and Oxytetracycline Drugs with Nucleic Acid Bases and Aromatic Amino Acids

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Spectral studies are made on tetracycline and oxytetracycline drugs with purines, pyrimidines and amino acids. $\epsilon_{\nu_{\max}}$ vs HFMO (highest filled π -molecular orbital) plots give different stabilization energies for purines, pyrimidines and amino acids. Oxytetracycline gives stronger complexes with purines, pyrimidines and amino acids than the tetracycline. The thermodynamic functions, ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° , have been calculated from the spectral data. Reasonable linear relationships have been found between ΔH° and ΔS° or ΔG° and ΔH° for these systems. The contribution of the dative bond wave function has been calculated for each complex in the ground state indicating the formation of charge-transfer complex of the order of 6-14%.

THE action of antibiotics¹ upon microorganisms may be either bacteriostatic or bactericidal. The mechanism through which the antibiotics act upon microorganisms is not fully clear. It is generally believed that the bacteriostatic effects arise from the interaction of antibiotics with bacterial enzymes, while the bactericidal effects originate in the interaction of antibiotics with cell nuclei. Molecular biologists have theorized that this interaction is due to complex formation between antibiotics and proteins on one hand and nucleic acids on the other, thereby suppressing the normal biological activity of proteins and nucleic acids. Some experimental support for this theory can be provided if the existence of molecular complexes of antibiotics with nucleic acids could be demonstrated by physical measurements. With this object in view systems containing antibiotics tetracycline and oxytetracycline, with purines, pyrimidines and amino acids in dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) and dimethyl formamide (DMF) were studied and the results are reported here. Similar studies were made in water, ethylene glycol and propylene glycol where the interaction was shown to be of charge-transfer type².

Since tetracycline and oxytetracycline have intense absorption bands in the near ultraviolet region at 363 nm and 365 nm, respectively optical methods may be used conveniently for the study of molecular complexes in these systems. We have used four aromatic amino acids phenyl alanine tryptophan, tyrosine and histidine; four purines adenine, guanine, xanthine and hypoxanthine and three pyrimidines cytosine, thymine and uracil in the present investigation.

Experimental

All the purines, pyrimidines and amino acids used are products of E. Merck, Darmstadt, B. D. H., England and Loba Chemical, Austria. They were

of A. R. grade and used without further purification. The solvents used were of E. Merck quality. They were carefully dried and freshly distilled just before the experiments. Since traces of moisture in the solvents give completely erratic results, particular care was taken about the purification of the solvents. Tetracycline and oxytetracycline were obtained from Sigma Company, St. Louis, U. S. A. and used directly without further purification.

All spectral data were taken in Beckman model DU spectrophotometer provided with a thermostatic arrangement, using matched pairs of stoppered silica cells. Measurements with strongly absorbing systems were made in 1 cm cells whereas 10 cm cells were used when the intensity of absorption was low. Measurements were made at four different temperatures namely 23, 40, 50 and 60°. The thermostatic arrangements were kept under such control that the variation of temperature did not exceed $\pm 1^\circ$.

The concentrations of the donors were 10^{-5} mole/litre and those of drugs were 10^{-5} mole/litre.

Results and Discussions

The absorption spectra of tetracycline and adenine-tetracycline mixture in DMSO is given in Fig. 1. The tetracycline shows a peak at 363 nm, while adenine-tetracycline mixture shows two peaks at 363 nm and 376 nm. Adenine itself, in DMSO, has no absorption band in this region. As the adenine concentration is increased at a fixed tetracycline concentration, the optical density of the band at 376 nm increases and that at 363 nm diminishes. Evidently, the band at 376 nm arises from a molecular complex between tetracycline and adenine. When balanced against the same concentration of tetracycline in DMSO the band appears at 385 nm, definitely establishing a red shift in the spectra with respect to tetracycline band (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Similar measurements were made with other purines, pyrimidines and amino acids and new bands were detected in all the cases. Oxytetracycline behaved in a similar fashion. The relevant data are summarised in Tables 1 and 2.

The spectral measurements at a fixed concentration of antibiotic but different concentrations of purines, pyrimidines and amino acids may be utilised to determine the equilibrium constant for complex formation. Since free antibiotic absorb quite strongly at the complex band, the simple Benesi-Hildebrand⁸ treatment cannot be used in the present case. For these types of situation de Maine⁴ has worked out an iterative method for estimating equilibrium constants, K_c , from optical density measurements at complex band. About four/five iterations were necessary to get self consistency in K_c values. The calculated values are also given in Tables 1 and 2. A perfect linearity of $[A]/(O.D.)_c$ versus $1/[D]$ plots, where $[A]$ is the

concentration of antibiotic and $[D]$ the concentration of donors, shows that the complexes studied are of 1 : 1 type.

The thermodynamic functions ΔH° , ΔS° and ΔG° connected with the complex formation are calculated from the changes in formation constant with temperature by Van't Hoff equation (Tables 1 and 2).

It appears from the K_c values recorded in Tables 1 and 2 that antibiotics tetracycline and oxytetracycline form strong complexes with purines, pyrimidines and aromatic amino acids. So, both proteins and nucleic acid bases form strong complexes with these antibiotics. From the points of view of drug action, as stated earlier, these findings obviously mean that tetracycline and oxytetracycline will have both bactericidal and bacteriostatic effects. As a matter of fact, Snell and Cheng⁹ reported that tetracyclines are bacteriostatic at low concentrations but bactericidal at higher concentrations; they decrease protein synthesis at low concentrations and nucleic acid formation at higher concentrations. It is also evident (Tables 1 and 2) that oxytetracycline forms much stronger complexes with purines, pyrimidines and amino acids than those formed by tetracycline. This may account for the selectivity of oxytetracycline as compared to tetracycline, although they have similar biological behaviour.

It must be stated categorically that this is no one-to-one correlation between the actual biological reactions and the systems studied in the present investigation. This is only a good model system reproducing reasonably well some of the findings in biological system.

Now a word about the nature of the forces involved in molecular complex formation. Since the appearance of the famous book on molecular biology by Szent-Györgyi⁶, a majority of workers support the proposition that the interaction in many biological processes is charge-transfer in nature. So the question is whether the molecular complexes studied in the present case can be considered as charge-transfer complexes.

One way of verifying this is to plot $h\nu_{transition}$ against the ionization energies of the purines, pyrimidines and amino acids, considering the antibiotics as acceptors. The experimental ionization energies of all the purines, pyrimidines and amino acids are not available in the literature. However, we can take the energy of the highest filled π -molecular orbital, HFMO/ β , which is related to the ionization energies of the respective compounds as calculated by Pullman and Pullman⁷. Such curves are shown in Fig. 3. The relevant data are given in Table 3. It may be observed that the plot is fairly linear for purine-, pyrimidine-tetracycline systems and for amino acid-tetracycline system. The same is true for the oxytetracycline acceptor as is evident from Fig. 4.

TABLE I—SOLVENT DMSO

Donors	OT* λ _{max} nm	-ΔH° K Joule mole ⁻¹		-ΔS° Joule mole ⁻¹ deg ⁻¹		-ΔG° K Joule mole ⁻¹	Temp. °C	K _c L mole ⁻¹		ε _c L mole ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹			
		Tetra- cycline	Oxytetra- cycline	Tetra- cycline	Oxytetra- cycline			Tetra- cycline	Oxytetra- cycline	Tetra- cycline	Oxytetra- cycline		
Adenine	385	388	25.11 ± 0.28	26.58 ± 0.15	9.54 ± 0.08	4.19 ± 0.04	22.26 ± 0.06	25.32 ± 0.02	23	70 ± 2	130 ± 5	14,290 ± 685	15,038 ± 13
	386	389	26.32 ± 0.18	27.33 ± 0.17	10.71 ± 0.09	5.73 ± 0.03	23.10 ± 0.04	23.61 ± 0.03	40	17.8	47.9	14,218	14,706
	392	390	22.52 ± 0.19	23.94 ± 0.18	7.66 ± 0.04	3.05 ± 0.03	20.31 ± 0.08	23.02 ± 0.04	50	3.4	31.6	14,164	14,652
	397	404	28.12 ± 0.19	26.32 ± 0.10	14.52 ± 0.27	9.54 ± 0.07	23.81 ± 0.06	23.48 ± 0.05	60	2.4	19.2	14,194	14,599
Thymine	370	371	19.13 ± 0.09	21.26 ± 0.08	6.48 ± 0.04	3.67 ± 0.08	17.30 ± 0.05	18.79 ± 0.06	23	16 ± 0.05	55 ± 1	18,100 ± 190	20,000 ± 145
	371	375	23.94 ± 0.14	25.53 ± 0.09	8.03 ± 0.09	3.43 ± 0.05	21.51 ± 0.07	24.48 ± 0.05	40	9.04	31.5	17,699	19,048
	371	375	23.94 ± 0.14	25.53 ± 0.09	8.03 ± 0.09	3.43 ± 0.05	21.51 ± 0.07	24.48 ± 0.05	50	5.66	21.02	17,667	19,029
	371	375	23.94 ± 0.14	25.53 ± 0.09	8.03 ± 0.09	3.43 ± 0.05	21.51 ± 0.07	24.48 ± 0.05	60	3.42	10.51	17,543	19,026
Phenylalanine	400	398	23.94 ± 0.19	25.54 ± 0.04	5.73 ± 0.03	6.48 ± 0.06	22.22 ± 0.09	23.56 ± 0.07	23	119 ± 1	130 ± 0.5	13,333 ± 955	15,385 ± 95
	402	400	24.78 ± 0.16	27.33 ± 0.07	6.84 ± 0.07	7.66 ± 0.05	22.73 ± 0.03	25.07 ± 0.02	40	25.67	36.48	13,245	15,397
	402	400	24.78 ± 0.16	27.33 ± 0.07	6.84 ± 0.07	7.66 ± 0.05	22.73 ± 0.03	25.07 ± 0.02	50	21.15	24.40	13,286	15,326
	403	401	21.26 ± 0.12	25.52 ± 0.08	8.60 ± 0.09	3.80 ± 0.06	20.17 ± 0.05	21.34 ± 0.07	60	15.65	15.3	13,318	15,267
Histidine	403	401	21.26 ± 0.12	25.52 ± 0.08	8.60 ± 0.09	3.80 ± 0.06	20.17 ± 0.05	21.34 ± 0.07	23	61.2 ± 1.2	70.4 ± 2.4	11,770 ± 156	12,500 ± 353
	405	402	24.33 ± 0.17	21.26 ± 0.04	1.88 ± 0.07	3.43 ± 0.04	19.54 ± 0.09	20.21 ± 0.09	40	35.34	46.88	11,110	12,422
	405	402	24.33 ± 0.17	21.26 ± 0.04	1.88 ± 0.07	3.43 ± 0.04	19.54 ± 0.09	20.21 ± 0.09	50	18.11	31.84	11,050	13,414
	405	402	24.33 ± 0.17	21.26 ± 0.04	1.88 ± 0.07	3.43 ± 0.04	19.54 ± 0.09	20.21 ± 0.09	60	9.0	16.13	11,019	12,399
Tryptophan	405	402	24.33 ± 0.17	21.26 ± 0.04	1.88 ± 0.07	3.43 ± 0.04	19.54 ± 0.09	20.21 ± 0.09	23	49.5 ± 2.25	91 ± 1.66	9,999 ± 1304	12,384 ± 95
	405	402	24.33 ± 0.17	21.26 ± 0.04	1.88 ± 0.07	3.43 ± 0.04	19.54 ± 0.09	20.21 ± 0.09	40	32.64	36	9,804	11,111
	405	402	24.33 ± 0.17	21.26 ± 0.04	1.88 ± 0.07	3.43 ± 0.04	19.54 ± 0.09	20.21 ± 0.09	50	12.48	18.4	9,615	10,870
	405	402	24.33 ± 0.17	21.26 ± 0.04	1.88 ± 0.07	3.43 ± 0.04	19.54 ± 0.09	20.21 ± 0.09	60	8.4	7.4	9,524	10,811
Xanthine**	397	404	28.12 ± 0.19	26.32 ± 0.10	14.52 ± 0.27	9.54 ± 0.07	23.81 ± 0.06	23.48 ± 0.05	23	54 ± 0.05	93.8 ± 0.80	17,021 ± 103	19,193 ± 67
	397	404	28.12 ± 0.19	26.32 ± 0.10	14.52 ± 0.27	9.54 ± 0.07	23.81 ± 0.06	23.48 ± 0.05	40	36.8	40.2	16,667	18,181
	397	404	28.12 ± 0.19	26.32 ± 0.10	14.52 ± 0.27	9.54 ± 0.07	23.81 ± 0.06	23.48 ± 0.05	50	24.2	31.08	16,528	18,018
	397	404	28.12 ± 0.19	26.32 ± 0.10	14.52 ± 0.27	9.54 ± 0.07	23.81 ± 0.06	23.48 ± 0.05	60	12.15	15.68	14,460	17,857

* Calculated from absorption data of 4 different [Donors] + [Tetracycline] or [Oxytetracycline] solutions in DMSO. [Tetracycline] or [Oxytetracycline] = 1.0 - 1.85 × 10⁻⁵ mole/l; [Donors] varied from 0.0495 to 0.095 moles/l using 1 cm cells.

** Xanthine using 10 cm cells.

TABLE 2—SOLVENT DMF

Donors	OT* λ_{max} nm	- ΔH° K Joule mole ⁻¹		- ΔS° Joule mole ⁻¹ deg ⁻¹		- ΔG° K Joule mole ⁻¹		Temp. °C	K _o L mole ⁻¹		L mole ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	
		Tetra- cycline	Oxytetra- cycline	Tetra- cycline	Oxytetra- cycline	Tetra- cycline	Oxytetra- cycline		Tetra- cycline	Oxytetra- cycline		
Adenine	390	40.22 ± 0.28	32.39 ± 0.34	3.85 ± 0.09	18.75 ± 0.09	37.08 ± 0.04	26.79 ± 0.06	23	39.6 ± 1	47.5 ± 0.75	18,383 ± 182	14,708 ± 520
								40	16	11.2	12,500	14,285
								50	12.80	5.64	12,422	14,184
								60	6.44	3.32	12,414	14,174
Guanine	400	36.30 ± 0.46	29.46 ± 0.26	4.01 ± 0.05	18.90 ± 0.09	39.09 ± 0.03	24.06 ± 0.05	23	30 ± 0.5	40 ± 1	10,000 ± 82	11,111 ± 125
								40	16.8	19	9,528	10,989
								50	10.55	7.26	9,478	10,964
								60	7	3.65	9,438	10,958
Hypoxanthine	403	31.89 ± 0.55	27.33 ± 0.09	3.43 ± 0.09	17.30 ± 0.05	30.89 ± 0.07	22.89 ± 0.07	23	28 ± 0.60	40.3 ± 0.30	12,821 ± 820	12,422 ± 45
								40	16.4	14	12,195	11,764
								50	10	7	12,121	11,695
								60	7.2	5	12,084	11,637
Xanthine**	406	23.35 ± 0.18	25.11 ± 0.04	15.69 ± 0.69	9.58 ± 0.02	18.66 ± 0.03	22.26 ± 0.08	23	27.2 ± 0.08	42.94 ± 0.94	15,384 ± 50	17,700 ± 25
								40	20.86	35.2	15,253	16,667
								50	8	28.86	15,151	16,529
								60	3.6	13.42	15,050	16,502
Thymine	395	36.34 ± 0.44	29.46 ± 0.21	3.60 ± 0.18	16.07 ± 0.09	37.31 ± 0.07	24.65 ± 0.05	23	41.8 ± 1.4	44 ± 1	10,526 ± 950	13,698 ± 101
								40	18	15	10,000	13,333
								50	12.24	10.57	9,803	13,245
								60	8.2	4.56	9,756	13,157
Uracil	395	34.82 ± 0.69	28.12 ± 0.19	3.64 ± 0.09	19.83 ± 0.04	33.73 ± 0.03	23.52 ± 0.06	23	28.08 ± 0.28	37.5 ± 0.5	13,423 ± 80	13,333 ± 300
								40	18	16	13,333	12,500
								50	7.6	8	13,245	12,422
								60	3.4	5	12,987	12,414
Phenylalanine	393	32.86 ± 0.27	29.46 ± 0.21	14.56 ± 0.14	16.11 ± 0.09	28.46 ± 0.05	24.65 ± 0.07	23	172.5 ± 0.5	180 ± 4	12,820 ± 50	13,333 ± 19
								40	28	20.5	12,500	13,245
								50	20	8.24	12,422	13,236
								60	8	4.16	12,414	13,201
Tyrosine	395	34.49 ± 0.24	30.97 ± 0.07	16.49 ± 0.09	17.20 ± 0.07	33.23 ± 0.03	25.78 ± 0.08	23	147 ± 3	162 ± 3.5	9,091 ± 125	11,111 ± 25
								40	40	21.6	9,090	11,110
								50	15.7	11	8,695	11,049
								60	5	4.34	8,658	11,043
Histidine	396	27.33 ± 0.19	27.33 ± 0.19	13.22 ± 0.13	14.52 ± 0.05	26.07 ± 0.04	23.02 ± 0.04	23	98 ± 2	126 ± 1	10,204	12,048 ± 45
								40	32	15.3	10,152	11,764
								50	14	10.26	10,147	11,695
								60	7	3.44	10,141	11,689
Tryptophan	400	23.94 ± 0.18	26.37 ± 0.04	11.46 ± 0.06	13.81 ± 0.03	20.51 ± 0.05	22.22 ± 0.06	23	161 ± 1	179 ± 0.54	11,765 ± 62	12,500 ± 55
								40	24.6	29.4	11,049	12,422
								50	12.67	13.66	11,043	12,414
								60	3.63	8.48	11,019	12,407

* Calculated from absorption data of 4 different [Donors] + [Tetracycline] or [Oxytetracycline] solutions in DMF; [Tetracycline] or [Oxytetracycline] = 1.0 - 1.85 × 10⁻⁵ mole/l; [Donors] varied from 0.0435 to 0.095 mole/l using 1 cm cells.

** Xanthine using 10 cm cells.

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Donors	Solvent DMSO $\nu \times 10^{-3} (\text{cm}^{-1})$		Solvent DMF $\nu \times 10^{-3} (\text{cm}^{-1})$		HFMO (β)
	Tetra- cycline	Oxytetra- cycline	Tetra- cycline	Oxytetra- cycline	
Adenine	25.97	25.77	25.64	25.25	0.486
Guanine	25.84	25.71	25.00	25.00	0.307
Xanthine	25.19	24.75	24.87	24.63	0.397
Hypoxanthine	25.51	25.64	25.00	24.81	0.402
Cytosine	25.64	25.84	25.31	25.12	0.595
Thymine	27.03	26.95	25.77	25.31	0.510
Uracil	26.95	26.67	26.04	25.97	0.597
Phenylalanine	25.00	25.13	25.64	25.44	0.908
Tyrosine	24.88	25.00	25.51	25.31	0.792
Histidine	24.81	24.94	25.31	25.25	0.660
Tryptophan	24.69	24.87	25.00	25.06	0.534

The reason for the two different plots for the two systems is obvious. The energy of charge-transfer transition is given as

$$h\nu_{\text{CT}} = I_D - E_A - \Delta.$$

where I_D is the ionization energy of the donor, E_A the electron affinity of the acceptor and Δ is the stabilization energy of the donor-acceptor pair.

The linear $h\nu_{\text{transition}}$ vs HFMO plot indicates a constant value for Δ . This may be true for chemically allied donors but is not certainly valid for completely chemically dissimilar donors like purines, pyrimidines and amino acids.

We may conclude that linear $h\nu_{\text{transition}}$ vs HFMO plots indicate that the purines, pyrimidines and amino acids are acting as donors and tetracycline and oxytetracycline as acceptors in the molecular complexes in two solvents and the complex is of charge-transfer type.

Regarding the temperature variation, we may observe that the formation constants, K_o , and the extinction coefficient, ϵ_o , both diminish with rise of temperature. In Figs. 5, 6, 7 and 8 plots of $-\Delta S^\circ$ vs $-\Delta H^\circ$ and ΔG° vs $-\Delta H^\circ$ are shown. These are found to be fairly linear as reported earlier⁸. The position of equilibrium showed reversibility with temperature. The negative enthalpy term and the intensification of band on cooling clearly indicate the charge-transfer nature of the complex⁹.

Fig. 5

Fig. 6

Fig. 7

As is observed, the formation constants increase with increase¹⁰⁻¹³ in dielectric constant of the medium for the purines and pyrimidines whereas these decrease¹⁴ with increase in the dielectric constant of the medium for the amino acids. Since charge transfer complexation takes place on a molecular level, the formation constant may be expected to be independent of the bulk dielectric constant. If the electrostatic interaction holds the molecules together, the formation constant will depend strongly on the dielectric constant of the medium and in fact will be lowered with an increase in the dielectric constant of the medium¹⁴. However, considering the various factors contributing to the formation of charge-transfer complexes, it is practically difficult to separate the influence of one factor from the others. Moreover, the high dielectric constants of the solvents used should have a direct impact also. As previously¹⁵ pointed out, the model developed from the concept of reaction field¹⁶, though capable of describing approximately the interaction between a solute and weakly polar solvents, becomes too crude an approximation for polar solvent.

TABLE 4—SOLVENT DMSO : ESTIMATED CONTRIBUTION OF THE DATIVE BOND WAVE FUNCTION FOR PURINES, PYRIMIDINES AND AMINO ACIDS+TETRACYCLINE/OXYTETRACYCLINE

Donors	$-\Delta H^\circ$ (ev)		$h\nu_{CT}$ (ev)		b^2/a^2	
	Tetracycline	Oxytetracycline	Tetracycline	Oxytetracycline	Tetracycline	Oxytetracycline
	Adenine	0.26	0.27	3.22	3.20	0.0807
Guanine	0.27	0.28	3.20	3.19	0.0850	0.0888
Hypoxanthine	0.23	0.27	3.17	3.07	0.0737	0.0888
Xanthine	0.29	0.25	3.13	3.18	0.0982	0.0779
Thymine	0.20	0.26	3.33	3.34	0.0694	0.0825
Uracil	0.25	0.22	3.34	3.31	0.0741	0.0659
Phenylalanine	0.25	0.26	3.10	3.12	0.0799	0.0848
Tyrosine	0.26	0.23	3.09	3.10	0.0832	0.0913
Histidine	0.22	0.23	3.08	3.09	0.0715	0.0754
Tryptophan	0.21	0.22	3.06	3.08	0.0681	0.0714

TABLE 5—SOLVENT DMF : ESTIMATED CONTRIBUTION OF THE DATIVE BOND WAVE FUNCTION FOR PURINES, PYRIMIDINES AND AMINO ACIDS+TETRACYCLINE/OXYTETRACYCLINE

Donors	$-\Delta H^\circ$ (ev)		$h\nu_{CT}$ (ev)		b^2/a^2	
	Tetracycline	Oxytetracycline	Tetracycline	Oxytetracycline	Tetracycline	Oxytetracycline
	Adenine	0.42	0.32	3.18	3.13	0.1309
Guanine	0.40	0.30	3.10	3.11	0.1278	0.0982
Hypoxanthine	0.33	0.28	3.08	3.09	0.1065	0.0917
Xanthine	0.24	0.26	3.08	3.05	0.0783	0.0851
Thymine	0.39	0.30	3.20	3.14	0.1242	0.0972
Uracil	0.36	0.29	3.23	3.22	0.1116	0.0904
Phenylalanine	0.34	0.30	3.18	3.16	0.1070	0.0967
Tyrosine	0.35	0.32	3.17	3.14	0.1129	0.1021
Histidine	0.28	0.28	3.14	3.13	0.0902	0.0903
Tryptophan	0.25	0.27	3.10	3.20	0.0799	0.0878

Fig. 8

According to Mulliken¹⁷, the ground state and excited state of the molecular complex may be written as

$$\psi_N(DA) = a\psi_0(DA) + b\psi_1(D^+A^-)$$

$$\text{and } \psi_E(DA) = a^*\psi_1(D^+A^-) - b^*\psi_0(DA)$$

where $\psi_0(DA)$ is the no-bond wave function and ψ_1 the dative bond wave function. For weak complexes $a \gg b$, $a^* \gg b^*$; moreover $a^* \sim a$ and $b^* \sim b$. The ratio b^2/a^2 can be calculated from the observed heat of formation and position of CT bands following Ketelaar¹⁸ and Tamres and Brandon⁸.

$$b^2/a^2 \approx -\frac{\Delta H_0}{h\nu}$$

These values are listed in Tables 4 and 5. It appears that the charge-transfer interactions are of the order of 6-14%.

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